

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Trucks are not as important as patients, but through the Toyota Production System and lean principles, car manufacturers often put far more effort into supporting their front-line staff than many hospitals. This is a shame, because properly applied, lean tools like work standardization, 5S, visualization and kanban can deliver great results in the medical field. A hospital lean transformation can save money and, more importantly, lives.

Healthcare is ripe for lean

BY MOHAMMED HAMED AHMED SOLIMAN

Lean thinking is a set of concepts, strategies, principles and tools that can deliver the most value for customers while consuming the fewest resources and fully using the knowledge and skills of the workforce. As defined by Mark Graban, author of *Lean Hospitals: Improving Quality, Patient Safety and Employee Engagement*, lean healthcare means delivering the most value to patients while consuming the least resources and maximizing the use of people skills and knowledge. Lean healthcare strives to improve quality, prevent errors and make patients safer, all while removing wastes and the possibility of defects.

After all, defects in healthcare can be catastrophic, threaten lives and directly affect patient safety. Defects or mistakes can lead to improper sterilization, dispensing the wrong drugs to the wrong patient, incorrect drug dosages or improper diagnosis – all of which can be hazardous to your patients' health.

Proof from the front lines

Lean can apply throughout a medical system: Opportunities for improvements can be found in laboratories, clinics, diagnosis rooms, operating rooms, surgical rooms and intensive care units.

Before lean, "improvement" meant doing work faster. But accelerating work doesn't necessarily make things better and, in fact, can decrease quality. Making people work faster can overburden them, leading to an unbalanced workload that can trigger more mistakes, errors and create wastes in other linked areas.

Lean, on the other hand, works by taking out wastes and the non-value-added steps to improve value-added processes. Therefore, lean healthcare is not about cutting costs by reducing the level of service and the quality of care. Instead, lean healthcare puts more value in patient care. Improving quality is the key to saving costs.

Graban highlighted some excellent achievements in *Lean Hospitals*.

For example, Allegheny Hospital in Pennsylvania reduced central line bloodstream infections by 76 percent, reducing patient deaths from these problems by

95 percent and saving \$1 million. The University of Pennsylvania Medical Center reduced hospital-acquired infections, saving 57 lives, reducing how long patients remained in intensive care and cutting costs by more than \$5 million over two years. ThedaCare in Wisconsin reduced patient waiting time for nonemergent orthopedic surgery from 14 weeks to 31 hours, improving its inpatient satisfaction score from 68 percent to 90 percent. Palo Alto Medical Foundation in California reduced waiting time for screening colonoscopies from six weeks to less than 24 hours while reducing cost per patient by 9.5 percent.

Lab productivity can be increased by improving turnaround time, the time from when a patient's sample is drawn until he or she learns the results. Poor lab layout blocks the flow of samples. Many labs use batch processing, which keeps samples waiting before inspection and diagnosis.

Replacing batch processing with one-piece flow can save thousands of dollars and dramatically reduce turnaround time. Graban's *Lean Hospitals* cited a case where moving the specimen collection point in the lab closer to the diagnostic device slashed laboratory turnaround time by 29 percent.

Speedier turnaround time also benefits surgical centers. Many hospitals prepare for the next surgery in the downtime between procedures. Applying the Toyota Production System's tool known as single minute exchange of die (SMED) prepares the next room for surgery while the current one is in process, gathering all the tools and instruments into their proper places. This reduces expensive downtime.

These achievements prove that applying lean in healthcare can deliver results in terms of patient safety and care, all while reducing costs.

It's all about the waste

The eight types of waste (the traditional seven – time, inventory, movement, waiting, overproduction, overprocessing and defects – plus wasted talent) provide

many opportunities for improvement in healthcare.

In medical care, any process that doesn't provide patient care should be considered nonvalue-added. Examples include doctors who stand in the diagnosis room waiting for someone to bring a missing instrument, rework caused by defects (bringing the wrong drug or incorrect dosage, which can harm patients), storing drugs for adults in the newborn intensive care unit and failed blood draws that need to be redone.

Underutilization of human talent can include a laboratory physician who draws specimens or loads them on the diagnostic device. Young assistants can do those jobs while the physician analyzes and troubleshoots the test results.

Nurses should spend their time charting with patients, discussing their health with them, describing proper drug dosage and administration and other in-patient care issues. Unfortunately, many nurses waste a lot of time walking between departments, searching for tools and bringing patients drugs. Some of these activities can be done by people with less expertise to save money and allow nurses more time with patients.

One simple process improvement involves bags – yes, bags. In some hospitals, nurses carry many of their tools and instruments in a waist bag, which saves them from walking here and there to find the necessary items.

Such an improvement also helps reduce waiting, the most common waste in all hospitals. The waste of waiting is acutely obvious to patients who wait to make an appointment, wait when they arrive at the office, wait to pay bills and wait to get discharged. Doctors often wait for the tools they need. Others wait for pharmacy orders, medications and tools that are properly sterilized. All of this delays patient care.

Hospital layout greatly affects transportation waste. A nurse on an intensive care unit might average walking from 7 to 9 kilometers per day. Proper layouts minimize this, along with reducing transportation time for patients,

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specimens and other hospital staff.

Wasted motion, which can refer to workplace ergonomics, also applies in hospitals. If tools and instruments aren't handy, people will move here and there searching for them.

Medical overproduction usually involves unnecessary tests and checkups. Overproducing information that is not useful or won't be used is a waste that can delay treatment and add costs.

Hospitals also face the traditional trade-off between keeping limited inventory without running out of necessary supplies. Lean encourages having the right supplies and inventory on hand to ensure the right patient care can be delivered on time. A lean tool like kanban can ensure the right supplies are available in the right place at the right time.

Overprocessing is replete in medical care, particularly with patients who have to describe their symptoms multiple times – not just in follow-up visits,

but on the same trip. Another example involves labs that use more of the hypo-osmotic swelling solution when evaluating the sperm membrane to assess sperm vitality. The extra use doesn't make a difference and is just waste. And some labs leave sperm in the solution longer than necessary, while less than a minute is more than sufficient.

In her book *Value Stream Mapping for HealthCare Made Easy*, Cindy Jimmerson showed how mapping the process can tackle wastes in patient treatment processes. The process of patient treatment starts when the patient feels symptoms, continues with the patient receiving care and ends with bill payment. The process may include making appointments to meet doctors, screenings and analysis, delivering test results and receiving treatment, along with follow-ups until full cure.

Standardization is the foundation

Standardized work is a foundation

of lean and is a key for good quality. Without standardization, all of your nurses, technicians, physicians and administrative staff will perform tasks differently. This makes tracking the source of errors difficult. Without standardization, the traditional gemba walk – leaders examining where the work is done and analyzing processes – is pointless.

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The standard should involve the work elements, the work sequence, the tools, equipment and material needed and the amount of time it should take. Without those elements, workers will have no way of knowing whether they have improved. Doing the job differently every time makes consistent quality and productivity impossible.

A lack of standards in processes can lead to miserable results. CBC News reported on Northern Health, a hospital in England, that performed procedures on 10,000 patients over three years with improperly cleaned endoscopes.

Proper standardization removes wastes, maintains quality, controls variation and improves productivity. Improper standardization, however, can amplify problems. Forms that patients must fill out and sign often are a frustrating holdup, so a standardization process that adds to these forms will not improve things.

Great hospitals in the United States and Japan have introduced standards through all levels, including their CEOs, presidents and directors. While senior leaders likely will have less of their time covered by standardized work, many organizations have a standard for what leaders and managers should look for in gemba walks. A standardized work process should be used to train the new staff and educate patients.

These guidelines can help your healthcare center write the right standards:

1. Don't rely on previous time studies recorded at the engineering office.
2. Eliminate any wasted motion and waiting times. Don't include any walking time in the work elements. Don't include any non-value-added work.
3. Measure the time of each work element separately. Don't include only the total time of the job.
4. Standards should be an output from process mapping. Human time usually should be separated from the process time.
5. Allow people to share their ideas for improving their work.
6. Use auditing to ensure people are working to the standard. If the standard is not being followed, leaders must ask why. Leaders should work with employees to improve standards and remove any obstacle.
7. Standardization should be a part of any improvement efforts to achieve the organization's vision and goals. Forcing people to follow a standard because management needs to make things look better is not what adds value to the customer.

Standardizing common daily tasks frees up healthcare professionals who can use that time to focus on value-added work, proactively solving uncommon problems and daily pop-ups.

Standards guard against calamity

Industrial and systems engineers are often reminded that patients aren't widgets, so manufacturing principles might not always apply. And it's true that standardization may not be done for all processes. But standardization can benefit many processes that affect patient safety. Hospitals should have common processes for hand washing and hygiene, preparation steps for cardiac surgery, labeling patient specimens, administering medication, communicating with patients and cleaning and disinfecting patient rooms.

Examples of standardization problems abound in healthcare. And none are more tragic than those that affect life at its beginning.

Take the case of one hospital that performs intracytoplasmic sperm injections (ICSI). On the day the clinic retrieves the woman's eggs, the couple has to wait for three hours in the patient room to sign forms related to embryo cryopreservation. While the routine form was necessary, the waiting time is unacceptable. If the hospital does 20 ICSI operations per day, this is 60 hours of waste that will delay patient discharge and keep rooms from opening up for new patients.

Standardization also can benefit the process of labeling patient specimens. This is a critical process where incorrect labeling can lead to catastrophe.

A recent article published by The American Society of Reproductive Medicine maintained that fertility clinics have an ethical obligation to disclose mistakes that could result in babies born with a "different genetic parentage than intended." Incorrect labeling could lead to inseminating a woman with the wrong sperm, combining the wrong sperm with the wrong eggs or transferring the wrong embryos to the

wrong uterus – devastating errors that can result in babies intended for other couples being born by someone else.

Such calamities, experts insist, are rare. The body representing Canada's largely for-profit fertility industry says it is unaware of any cases of "misdirected" embryos, but a smattering of reports of in-vitro fertilization (IVF) mix-ups in the United States and elsewhere have led to emotionally wrought battles to determine legal parentage and custody.

In 1999, a New York State woman of Italian descent gave birth to twin boys – one white, the other black. Reportedly, the clinic hadn't properly flushed the pipette between transfers. In 2015, a woman in Poland gave birth to another woman's child after her husband's sperm was mistakenly used to fertilize someone else's egg.

Many fertility centers use barcodes made from polysilicon, the same material used in glass, to prevent such IVF mix-ups. Each tag is about one-tenth the width of a human egg and can be marked with patterns representing an eight-digit binary code, providing 256 possible combinations.

To attach these barcodes to eggs, clinics use a protein that binds the carbohydrates on the cell's outer surface. Following a standard process to check that the right egg is being used, the barcode is read using a microscope before the IVF procedure. The tag doesn't affect the egg or the embryo and is shed by the embryo when implanted into the womb.

Communication can be another key standard. Adam International Hospital is a fertility center in Egypt that standardizes what doctors and assistants say in the operating room before surgery starts. This has had a remarkable result on patients' satisfaction and morale. In many cases, educating patients on their medications is very necessary. It usually includes how to take the dosage and the possible side effects, and proper communication is vital.

Communicating efficiently with patients and families before surgery

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also adds value to healthcare services. Acknowledge the person by name, introduce yourself, discuss the duration of stay, explain what you are doing and, finally, thank them.

Some surgical processes that are done without anesthesia require patient education and clear instructions. Take the IVF embryo transfer operation. The gynecologist should describe the process to the patient and give her clear instructions. For example, female patients must lie on their back for one hour after this procedure. She cannot move and must keep her head in a flat position. And for the following few days, she must take several precautions and follow a particular diet.

Failure to adhere to these instructions could cause the embryo implantation to fail.

The proper lean mindset

The proper mindset is important for a lean culture to flourish.

As Liker described in *The Toyota Way*, one Toyota management principle is to “base your management decision on long-term financial benefit even at the expense of the short-term financial gain.”

Likewise, adding more value to patients is a long-term investment. Short-term cost reduction thinking can sabotage patient morale and satisfaction and delay treatment.

For example, for the purpose of economy, some laboratories process certain tests once every two weeks. But this can delay in ways that will cost the hospital far more than any short-term savings. One couple had worked for three years but still had not achieved pregnancy. Before doing an ICSI procedure, a fertility clinic specialist wanted to assess the sperms’ DNA fragmentation to determine their fertilization ability, a dispersion test that should take labs no more than two days.

But since the lab always waited until it had several specimens to run the test once or twice a month, the laboratory took five weeks to deliver the results. On top of that, after the results were in, the doctor had to prescribe antioxidant medicines for three months and repeat the test. That totals five-and-a-half months of waiting time for a process that should take three months and four days.

The frustrated couple decided to go to another place that provided more

value in patient care. This short-term financial thinking cost the fertility center much more than what it saved via batch processing of the sperm DNA test.

The proper lean healthcare tools

While tools help, management methods and philosophical concepts can assist your organization in choosing the right tools for your situation. Beyond standardization, the most common lean tools used in healthcare are 5S, visualization and kanban.

5S (sort, set in order, shine, standardize, sustain) is a method of creating a clean, well-organized and safe workplace free of clutter and wasted motion. 5S is about eliminating waste, not just making the place look nice.

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Sort eliminates items that haven’t been used for a while. Set in order organizes what is left in a way that will make it easier to find tools and materials. A good example of standardization in this arena is shadow boards. These boards outline tools so it’s easy to see which instruments are missing, insuring that every tool has a place and is returned after use.

Shine is about cleaning, which is all about infection control in healthcare.

Sustain audits to make sure things don't slip back.

Visual management is a problem-solving and prevention technique for reducing wastes. Examples include labels that warn about "Caution, hot contents" or "Warning! Risk of injury." Labeling specimens, as noted above, is a good example of visual control to prevent errors.

Many hospitals use visual management to identify the status of patients and their need to facilitate real-time decision-making. Tracking boards identify which rooms are open and let families know where their loved ones are. Some hospitals have automated this process and use large digital screens and software for managing the system.

Kanban is a method that often controls inventory buffers. The system yields fewer stock-outs and better material availability than other inventory management systems. In hospitals, kanban manages medical supplies, drugs, office supplies, linen and other commodities.

Kanban started to appear in healthcare in the late 1980s through the development of a two-bin system for medical supplies. When one compartment of supplies is empty, the nurses use the second (or backup compartment) and identify that a bin has been emptied.

Material handlers normally check nursing unit supplies on a fixed schedule. The handlers scan the kanban cards and transfer the requests to the material management's information system. For items stored in the central warehouse, the information system generates a pick list.

For direct purchases (items sourced externally), the system transmits a requisition to suppliers. Finally, material handlers deliver medical supplies directly into the empty bins, ensuring stock rotation in each unit.

Kanban systems save hospitals money. One medical center in Egypt reduced inventory holding value from \$3 million to less than \$800,000. Another reduced unplanned calls for materials by 50 percent.

Lean principles can be combined with other approaches like total production maintenance. TPM helps ensure that machines and instruments are working optimally. For instance, the ultrasonography machine is a critical instrument in gynecology clinics, where a failing or broken machine will delay patient treatment.

Analyzing failure prevents problems

A main goal of lean is to prevent problems before they happen, thus improving patient care. While analyzing the root cause of problems can prevent their reoccurrence, analyzing failure possibilities can prevent catastrophes.

A statistical quality tool like failure mode effect analysis (FMEA) can identify critical processes and the consequence of failure. Then it's up to management to use the best method to prevent those failures from occurring.

Many doctors track the causes of failure after they occur. While some failures can harm patients, others crush morale and cost money.

As noted above, pregnancy is a great example. When natural pregnancy is not possible, the next best choice is IVF treatment, which is complex and expensive, averaging \$15,000 for each fresh cycle in the United States. Insurance often doesn't cover the procedure, and sometimes it can be difficult to find an egg donor. The success rate, already low at 50 percent, also depends on the woman's age.

All of these factors can make a failure after treatment emotionally devastating to the couples involved. This makes the results shared in the paper "Successful Pregnancy Outcome in a Case of Protein S Deficiency" by D.M. Lalan, M.J. Jassawalla and S.A. Bhalerao interesting to people with such problems. The authors found that one out of every 500 to 3,000 women lose pregnancy due to protein S deficiency, which is an inherited form of thrombophilia.

Treatment for thrombophilia during pregnancy is easy and involves taking the correct medication and injections,

usually aspirin and heparin drugs. Testing costs about \$500 and can save couples who choose IVF a lot of time and heartbreak. If a couple decides to perform the additional tests, which cost \$500, they will be able to reduce the risk of failures instead of waiting until it happens and lose all the effort and money they spent in IVF. Doctors should have a standardized process for what questions they ask patients before treatment starts. Some diseases, including thrombophilia, can be genetic, so questions about historical family diseases should be on the list.

Understand that hospitals shouldn't overproduce diagnostics and tests and perform unnecessary checkups. That would be considered waste. But when there can be a high-risk result from not testing, the risk should be estimated and testing considered, as in the IVF-thrombophilia case.

Lean can bring positive change to healthcare

Healthcare professionals should not use lean approaches to seek direct cost reduction. Their main focus should be on adding more value to patients and improving quality – the cost improvements will come indirectly.

People aren't resistant to change, but they resist being changed. It's very clear that standardized work is the foundation of healthcare quality. But when applying lean, remember that we don't standardize processes for the sake of standardization. We do it for consistent quality and productivity. People shouldn't be forced to follow a standard without asking their input.

People aren't machines, and lean practitioners always should remember that respect for people is an important part of lean.

People aren't resistant to change, but they resist being changed, and lean tools won't work without the correct culture.

But it should be much easier to involve healthcare workers in a lean transformation, because unlike other sectors, people working in the medical industry are intrinsically motivated by the desire to help people and save lives. ❖